

Organizational climate and work engagement of employees of divine word colleges in Ilocos Region, Philippines

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ABSTRACT

The study aims to determine the correlation between organizational climate and work engagement of the employees. To strengthen the theory of the study, related literature was reviewed. The study used a descriptive correlational research design. To gather the data, questionnaires were used. The population of the study was all faculty and employees of the colleges in the Ilocos region. Since it is a quantitative study, the statistic was used to interpret the data. The weighted mean was used to determine the average mean of different organizational climate dimensions and different dimensions of work engagement, while Pearson *r* Correlation was used to determine the correlation between the organizational climate and work engagement of the employees. The results indicate that there is a significant correlation between organizational climate and work engagement of employees.

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Introduction

The game of business nowadays is competition and to win the competition, one must have the necessary strategy to play the game and win big (Wilson, 2012). As part of the game plan is human resources that have the necessary skills or experience to play or to work and if they do not have, they need to be sent for further training (Kenton, & Anderson, 2020). Given that all the elements that we have mentioned are in place, can we be assured that the vision, mission, and objectives will be achieved? It is not a guarantee if other factors such as organizational climate are not given attention. Issues on organizational climate had been sidelined in the management process because management has been focusing on efficiency management. Climate affects the temperature of the organization which eventually affects the employees' or workers' behavior, motivation, and work engagement (Chaudhary, et.al., 2013, Sunarsih & Helmiatin, 2017, Sambandam & Chockalingam, 2019). It affects the attainment of the vision, mission, and objective of the organization. If the employees are in a good mood, then it is expected to be good for the organization but if they do not feel good, then it is not going to be good for the organization. Thus, it affects the whole plan and can fail the organization.

The current research is concerned with the organizational climate of the Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos region. The success of any organization cannot be just relied on the factors that I have mentioned above but giving attention to a good organizational climate is very important too. Organizational climate is about the working environment. Issues such as clarity, responsibility, flexibility, rewards, and teamwork are intangible elements of the organization that managers should not neglect because it affects the motivation of employees to work (Drigo Consulting Group, 2003, Hay Group, 2003). Once the motivation is affected negatively or positively, then a logical consequence to the organization is expected. Motivated employees are happy to show up for work but demotivated employees are not happy to show up to work. Sometimes they show up but only for the sake of showing up but not to deliver the outputs.

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After the researcher has been working with schools for 25 years, one aspect of management function that has been neglected is organizational climate management. This aspect has been undermined by the management, they only focused on the big issues such as the issues of the strategic plan, vision, mission, objectives, key result areas, performance indicators, and strategies. Along the strategies, the managers have never touched on the environment of the school as one strategy to achieve the vision, mission, and objectives of the school. Managers seem to forget that the school environment affects everyone who is working in that school.

There have been few pieces of research done along with the organizational climate of the schools such as Hoy (2020), on school climate and outcomes, Thomas (1976), on the dimensions of school climate, and Batlolona (2018) on the school climate and teachers' performance improvement. However, their studies had presented different independent and dependent variables that are not related to the current study. There have been no studies yet related to measuring organizational climate and work engagement. Thus, the focus of the current study is to look into the organizational climate of the schools and how it affects the work engagement of the employees or faculty. The output of the current study helps the management to revise policies that can promote a better working climate of the school such as clarity, standards, responsibility, flexibility, rewards and recognition, and team commitment (Hey Group Research, 2003).

The purpose of the study is to investigate the correlation between the two variables, organizational climate and work engagement of employees. It specifically seeks to answer the following questions:

- i. What is the organizational climate of Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos region in terms of clarity, standards individual responsibility, flexibility, reward and recognition, team commitment?
- ii. What is the work engagement of employees of Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos Region in terms of cognitive engagement, effective engagement, conative engagement?
- iii. Is there a relationship between organizational climate and work engagement of employees?

The study assumes that the work climate affects the work engagement of employees and can be measured. The questionnaires in gathering the data for the study are valid and the responses of the employees are honest and objective.

Organizational climate play important role in supporting work engagement as Raja, et.al.(2019) pointed out that a good climate is a prerequisite for the success of the organization. Therefore, the study hypothesizes that organizational climate correlates with the work engagement of employees.

The study is limited to the faculty and employees of Divine Word Colleges in Ilocos Region and it covered only six dimensions of organizational climate as prescribed by Hey Group Research (2003) such as clarity, standards, responsibility, flexibility, rewards and recognition, and team commitment and three dimensions of work engagement which are cognitive, affective and conative dimensions

To carry out this study, the study is divided into several parts. The first part is the introduction in which the paper discusses the rationale of the study and objectives of the study. The second part is the related literature review that discusses the theories of the study. The third part is the methodology. This part discusses the research design, population of the study, the locale of the study, research instruments, data gathering procedures, and statistical treatment of data. The fourth part is the empirical data and analysis which discusses the findings of the study based on the problem of the study. The fifth part is the Result and discussion. This part discusses further findings and then the conclusion.

Literature Review

The main objective of the literature review is to gain an understanding of the current topic based on what other researchers and authors have found or discussed. This is to help the researcher gains more knowledge or understanding about the topic he/she is investigating (Western Sydney University, 2017). This part presents the pieces of literature that discuss the theories of the current study as the basis of the investigation of the current study.

Theoretical and Conceptual Framework

The Concept of Organizational Climate

Organizational climate is the working environment of the organization that may affect the employees. A good environment makes the employees happy, satisfied, and energized, and therefore employees are eager to work more for the company. It is an intangible aspect of the environment because it involves the emotional aspect of the employees. It is only the employees who feel it. Thus, organizational climate refers to employees' perceptions of organizational practices reported by people who work there (Rousseau, 20003). It is a situational characteristic that links to thoughts and feelings of workers that shape the common perception of employees as a result of organizational policies and procedures (Miller, 2003). This concept is similar to what Insel and Moos (1972) who argued earlier that it is a psychological and social dimension of the environment, including people's perceptions

Catto (2001) as cited from Evans, et.al (2007) contended that organizational climate is a perception that individuals have about the various aspect of the organizational environment. These perceptions are the results of organizational practices. According to Rousseau (1988), organizational climate is caused by several dimensions such as communication, conflicts (functional and dysfunctional), leadership (consistency, inconsistency, direction), and reward system. These aspects make up the organizational climate either

positive or negative. On one hand, a positive climate means that communication, leadership, relationships, and reward system are functioning well. On the other hand, when the climate is negative, it is an indication that those dimensions are not handled properly by the management.

Leadership is a key contributing factor to the stressful organizational climate. Applying an authoritarian leadership style can cause a problem to organizational climate as Rousseau (1988) argued that stressful organizational climate may happen if there is limited participation in decision making, use of punishment, and negative feedbacks rather than rewards and positive feedbacks, conflicts, or confrontation rather than problem-solving. When these kinds of environmental climate exist and are shared by all members of the organization, members of the organization can experience low morale and psychogenic illness and this can contribute to a stressful environment. These kinds of environments form employees' negative perceptions about the organization and these are no longer individual perceptions but it is already organizational perception about what is going on in the organization. And in the study of organizational climate, is not about individual perceptions taken into considerations but is a common perceptual agreement among employees in the organization (Glick, 1985).

Leadership and Organizational Climate

As I have argued earlier that organizational climate is a logical consequence of bad management and bad leadership. It is not born or given by the external environment but it is made by the management and therefore it can be managed. A positive or negative organizational climate is a product of leadership styles. The presence or the absence of clarity, responsibility, rewards, standards, support, and commitment can result in a positive or negative organizational climate (Stringer, 2002). These are also dimensions pointed out by Hey Group (2003) that contribute to organizational climate. According to Hay Group's research that 70 % of the employees' perception of organizational climate is a direct result of their manager's leadership styles. The climate that employees feel or experience at work is determined by how well their managers are planning, organizing, leading, and controlling. In other words, the level of leadership skills of managers can be measured by the environment of the organization as felt by the employees. According to Hay Group's research, that one of the most significant strengths of an effective is his/her ability to create a positive work climate and effective leaders are shifting leadership styles to create a positive work climate in the areas they manage. This has been confirmed by several studies such as Ko and Kang (2019) that different leadership styles affect the organizational climate and the study of Dulay and Karadag (2015) on the effect of leadership styles on the organizational climate.

Stringer (2002), Allen (2003) and Cameron and Smart (1998) are all arguing that a positive organizational climate is a direct result of effective leadership. The same point is also stressed by Yuan and Lee (2011) that produces high performance, satisfying and healthy work climate depends heavily on how managers go about leading employees. He reemphasized the points that have been raised by other researchers earlier that employees' perception of organizational climate is a direct result of managers' style or leadership styles. The climate that employees feel is not separated from the leadership itself. Likert (1967) has already contended that leadership styles contribute to organizational climate. There is strong evidence that points out the association between organizational climate leaders' ability to arouse motivation of employees and according to Likert (1967) that among the criterion of organizational properties, leadership styles throughout the organization is more important in affecting organizational outcome than factors such as employees' attitude and interest in the job.

Organizational Climate and Performance

One may not underestimate the importance of a positive organizational climate in any organization. Organizational climate either brings the organization up or bringing the organization down depending on the organizational climate. Hey Group (2003) in their research consistently found that when workers are enabled and motivated, they provide their best effort. Organizations with a good climate gain better performance and productivity compared to those organizations with a negative organizational climate. There is always a positive correlation between good organizational climate and profitability and sales in the business sector, patient satisfaction in the health care services, and students' advancement and academic achievement in educational institutions. Such finding is also confirmed by the study of Denis and Coban, (2016, cited by Hirlak, et.al 2018). Denis and Coban (2016) as cited by Hirlak, et.al (2018) found that organizational climate produces emotions and those emotions may increase the commitment of employees toward the organization or may decrease the commitment of employees toward the organization. Therefore, they suggested that the organizational climate should be designed to maximize organizational performance. Hirlak, et.al, (2018) also examined the correlation between organizational climate and employees' performance. They found that the sub-dimensions of organizational climate such as support, cohesion, intrinsic recognition, impartiality, and pressure have a positive and significant effect on employee creativity; and cohesion, pressure, intrinsic recognition, and employee creativity have a positive and significant effect on the employee performance.

James and Jones (1977) as cited by Kopelman, et.al (1990) and Putter (2010) have contended that organizational climate is tied to organizational productivity, profitability, sustainability, growth, and work engagement which is a function of an individual's behavior and according to Kopelman (1990) that there are three behaviors pertinent to organizational climate such as attachment, performance and citizen-related. These three behaviors will improve organizational productivity. Danisha (2017) in her study also confirmed the correlation between organizational climate and employees' performance in the Chemical industry in India. Individual performance is a result of a commitment to a job. Waktola (2014) discovered that organizational climate contributes to employees' organizational commitment and he singled out climate dimensions such as trust, support, autonomy, fairness, reward, and teamwork are important

to motivate employees' commitment to the organization. Among those dimensions, support and teamwork have the highest contribution to organizational commitment. This is also shown by the study of Chaudhary, et.al (2014) that organizational climate improves the work engagement of employees. The correlation between organizational climate and performance is not only applied in manufacturing companies but even in educational institutions as Palash and Deepak (2017) found that there is a significant correlation between the working environment and the performance of educational institutions.

Organizational Climate Characteristics Dimensions

There are many different organizational climate dimensions presented by different authors or researchers but for our investigation, we try to limit our investigation to the organizational climate as defined by Drigo Consulting Group (2003). Drigo Consulting Group (2003) has argued that organizational climate is a set of measurable properties of the work environment that are perceived by the people who live and work in it and influence their behavior and motivation. According to this group, there are several dimensions of organizational climate that have been considered to significantly impact the company's bottom line and these are flexibility, responsibility, standards, rewards, clarity, and team commitment. The same dimensions are also recommended by Hey Group (2003).

Clarity dimension

One can imagine if there is no clarity about things that we are going to pursue. Confusion and demotivation cannot be avoided as a result. It will not be considered an overstatement if Gore (2017) contended that the most important competency for a leader to possess is clarity. He considered clarity as to the greatest strategic advantage that an organization can have. Clarity simply means clearness, lucidity, freedom from ambiguity. Hey Group (2003) viewed that clarity means that employees understand their organization's mission and of their department and their unit contribution to achieving the common vision-mission. In this case, the organization should a clear expectation or target expected from members and a different unit of the organization.

The absence of clarity may create confusion and such confusion can be cleared through communication. Clarity encompasses a variety of communication. Thus, leadership or management needs to communicate the strategic direction of the organization as well as the direction of the department and its function (Gore, 2017). After communicating the strategic direction, the manager needs to explain how the work of different levels in the organization fits together to accomplish its mission. This may include explaining to the employees about the strategic direction and how to get there, policy guidelines to carry out their duties and responsibilities, and organizational structure that indicates the line of authority as well as the roles and responsibilities to be spelled out.

Standard dimension

Organizational standards mean the measurement or benchmark provided by the organization that everyone has to follow in carrying out their duties and responsibilities. These standards are used to measure the accomplishment of the work and to measure the results. Cen and Cenelec (2013) argues that many business use standard in their daily operation because it helps the business it ensures the quality and safety of the products or services and thus satisfy customers' satisfaction.

Concerning the organizational climate, standards mean the measurement to be used to gauge the quality work or the output that is expected of employees on a day to day basis. In other words, employees are expected to come out with the output daily and those outputs must be measured against the established standards. High standards begin with goals that are challenging but realistic. Beyond that, the goals must be measurable to indicate exactly what is expected of employees and therefore, enable the managers to hold his/her employees accountable for their work.

Individual Responsibility dimension

Litwin (1967) pointed out individual responsibility as one of the dimensions of organizational climate. What he meant by individual responsibility is individual freedom in carrying out their duties and responsibilities without external coercion. In other words, the managers must give employees the freedom to decide, work, and exercise their authority in their area of responsibility. Freedom or autonomy is experienced in two ways: the first, the employees that have the proper decision making power in their jobs. Second, employees are encouraged to be creative in finding ways that may lead to new, cheaper, and more efficient ways of doing things. This can also mean that the sole responsibility of the work is given to the employees and therefore there should be no interference from the management related to the work of employees (Balachandran & Thomas, 2007). This is not only to allow autonomy to grow with the employees but it also helps to reduce the burdens of the top management.

Flexibility dimension

Flexibility is one of the requirements that an organization needs to apply in its daily business. The reason is simple because the external environment is always changing. Rigidity in following the rules does not help the organization to take the opportunity of what is going on in the environment. That is why Rosen (n.d) defines organizational flexibility as adaptability, openness, and intensity at which an organism adapts to its changing environment. This is the only way to compete with other organizations. Along this line, LaMarco (2018), a management expert contends that rigidity can fail the organization because of the rapid changes in technology and the economy. Managers must be brave enough to violate the rules of policies when those policies are a hindrance to development.

In this study, flexibility dimensions of climate will measure employees' perceptions about the institution's desire to adapt to changes and employees' creativity. In this case, the interest is to find out if the managers are allowing the employees to express their ideas

and the management is willing to listen to their ideas and adapt them. In other words, managers need to allow the employees to decide on their creative ways even though it will mean violating the policies.

Reward and recognition dimension

One needs to understand the difference between rewards and recognition because often time people use the term interchangeably. When one talks about the reward he/she means for recognition or when he/she talks about the recognition he/she means it for the reward. Both terms are different. A reward is related to something tangible or something you can see, touch, and experience. Commonly, the reward is referring to monetary incentives given to employees because of good performance but it is not salary (Foronda, 2010). This is one of the strategies the companies are doing to attract good talents and motivate employees to perform better. Employees are motivated when they know that their efforts are rewarded and consequently it reinforces their good performance. While recognition is referring to intangible things in nature and it is not related to monetary value. This can be simple praise from management for an employee who has done a great job. But the two terms are always used together: reward and recognition to indicate that rewarding employees with money are not enough, there should also be emotional touch through praise or kind words accompanying the monetary rewards and advancement opportunities given to those who perform beyond standards.

Team Commitment dimension

A certain adage says, “Two heads are better than one”. This adage refers to teamwork. In other words, a result is better if the job is done by a group compared to a person who accomplishes the job. This concept is based on the finding of Woolley, et.al (2015) and her colleagues from Carnegie Mellon University. Based on their study, they found that “the intelligence of a group can exceed that of its members if the right conditions are met. “ (Wooly, et.al, 2015, cited by Luden, (2016). In their study, they found that the intelligence of the individual members did not predict group performance but collective intelligence predicts the performance (Luden, 2016, cited from Wooly, et.al, 2015).

The above finding becomes the basis of our belief that working as a team is better than working alone. Thus, the team dimension of organizational climate measures the feeling of everyone who works cooperatively to accomplish the goals (Hey Group, 2003, cited by Foronda, 2010). In this case, employees have been experiencing team commitment which they have seen through the actions shown by managers and employees, that managers cooperate with other managers, and employees work together with other co-employees to accomplish the team’s goals (Heatfield, 2019).

Work Engagement

Employee work engagement is not a matter of work attendance without any absences or being present in the workplace regularly but it is beyond physical presence in the workplace. Work engagement is about the cognitive, physical, and emotional or psychological connection to the work (Kuok & Taormina, 2017). Thus, work engagement is about the cognitive, physical, and emotional involvement of the person in the work. In other words, the person engaged in the work with his knowledge, his physical presence, and is emotionally engaged or the employees are psychologically connected to the work. These are the kinds of employees who are absorbed by their work and willing to dedicate their time and themselves to the work and are motivated to come out with quality performance and output (Bakker & Leiter, 2010). An engaged employee is giving everything to the work, his knowledge, physical and emotional attachment to the work. These are the employees who have full of ideas about their work, feeling delighted about what they are doing, and maintain a high level of energy and stamina to pursue the work on hand.

Based on the above concept of work engagement, therefore, measuring work engagement is not a single construct, or one dimension only such as physical construct only but it is a multidimensional construct because it measures, not only physical engagement or cognitive aspect of it but it involves the three aspects or dimensions such as cognitive, physical and emotional aspects too. There have been discussions along with this topic and disagreement about how to measure work engagement. On the one hand, one group says that work engagement is a single construct such as Maslach and Leiter (1997) as cited by Kuok and Taormina, (2017) and on the other hand, it is a multidimensional construct (Schaufeli, Salanova, Gonzalez-Roma & Bakker, 2002). Thus, for the current study, we agree that work engagement is a multidimensional construct. This is another development to my previous studies related to work engagement in which I saw work engagement as an emotional state and physical engagement and I have not included the cognitive aspect of it (Abun, et.al, 2017).

Independent Variables

Dependent Variables

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework; *Source: Hey Group (2003) and Drigo Consulting Group (2003) and Kuok and Taormina (2017)*

Figure 1 reflects the independent and dependent variables of the study. This is a cause and effect study which means the independent variable is the cause and the dependent variable is the effect (Thomas, 2020). In this case, when the independent variables are changed or manipulated, then consequently the dependent variables change (McLeod, 2019). There is a direct effect on the dependent variable. The conceptual framework of the current study reflects the correlation between the two variables, organizational climate and work engagement of the employee

Research and Methodology

The research methodology is the specific procedures to be followed in conducting an investigation. This is the basis for the determination of the quality and validity of the research (Wilkinson & Birmingham, 2003). Along with such a concept, this part presents the methodology of how this study was conducted or carried out. The study follows the prescribed rules of conducting an investigation and it means that there is research design, data gathering instruments, population, the locale of the study, data gathering procedures, and statistical treatment of data.

Research Design

The study used a descriptive assessment and correlational research design to determine the level of organizational climate and its effect on the work engagement of employees. Ariola (2006) contended that a descriptive correlation study is intended to describe the relationship among variables without seeking to establish a causal connection. While descriptive research is simply to describe a population, a situation, or a phenomenon. It is also used to describe profiles, frequency distribution, describe characteristics of people, situations, or phenomena. In short, it answers the question of what, when, how, where, and not why question (McCombes, 2020).

Data

The locale of the Study

The locale of the study was Divine Word Colleges in Ilocos Sur and Ilocos Norte.

Population

Those who answered the questionnaires are the faculty and employees of the Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos region. Since the number of faculty and employees are limited, therefore the total enumeration is applied which means that all employees were the respondents of the study.

Data Gathering instruments

The study adopted validated questionnaires of Hey Group Research (2003) on organizational climate and Kuok and Taormina (2017) on work engagement.

Data Gathering Procedures

Before the researcher distributes the questionnaires, letters were sent to the Presidents of the colleges to request them to allow the researcher to float his questionnaires in their respective institutions. Only after the approval of the President of the Colleges, the questionnaires were floated. In the process of collecting the data, the researcher requests employees' representatives to retrieve the data from different individual employees before they are submitted to the researcher.

Statistical Treatment of Data

To analyze the data, a descriptive and inferential statistic was used. The weighted mean was used to determine the level of organizational climate of the schools and the Pearson r was used to measure the correlation between organizational climate and work engagement of employees.

The following ranges of values with their descriptive interpretation will be used:

Range of Mean Values	Descriptive Interpretation
4.51 – 5.00	Strongly agree/Very High
3.51 – 4.50	Agree/High
2.51 – 3.50	Somewhat agree/Moderate
1.51 – 2.50	Disagree/Low
1.00 – 1.50	Strongly disagree/very low

Analysis

Scientific research is an evidence-based approach and so, the interpretation of information. Interpretation and analysis are solidly based on the raw data gathered through data-gathering instruments. However, though it is based on raw data, it does not give an absolute answer but only most like answer based on probability (Rouse, 2020). Based on this concept, this part is presenting the data

and analyses that were gathered through research questionnaires. The presentation is following the statement of the problem arrangement.

Problem 1: What is the organizational climate of Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos region in terms of:

- 1.1. Clarity
- 1.2. Standards
- 1.3. Individual responsibility
- 1.4. Flexibility
- 1.5. Reward and Recognition
- 1.6. Team commitment

Table 1: Organizational Climate Along with Clarity

Statements	Mean	Descriptive Interpretation
1. The strategic direction of the college, as well as the direction of the department and its functions, are clear	3.40	SWA/Moderate
2. The work of different levels in the college fits together to accomplish its mission	3.38	SWA/Moderate
3. Employees are involved in discussing the strategic direction and strategies on how to get there	3.17	SWA/Moderate
4. The employees understand the “whys” of the management’s decision related to employees well-being	3.10	SWA/Moderate
5. Policy guidelines are communicated to employees	3.26	SWA/Moderate
6. The lines of authority, as well as roles and responsibilities, are spelled out	3.30	SWA/Moderate
Composite Mean	3.27	SWA/Moderate

Source: Hey Group (2003)

Based on the data gathered, it shows that as a whole, the organizational climate of the Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos region along with *clarity dimension* is considered moderate (somewhat agree) which is reflected in its composite mean of 3.27. This composite mean indicates that the organizational climate of the Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos Region is not very high or high and it is also not very low or low but at a moderate level. Even when the items are taken singly, all are rated within the same level of interpretation which is “somewhat agree or moderate”, such as: “the strategic direction of the college, as well as the direction of the department and its functions, are clear (3.40), the work of different levels in the college fits together to accomplish its mission (3.38), employees are involved in discussing the strategic direction and strategies on how to get there (3.17), the employees understand the “whys” of the management’s decision related to employees well-being (3.10), policy guidelines are communicated to employees (3.26), and the lines of authority, as well as roles and responsibilities, are spelled out (3.30).

Such moderate level assessment reflects a case that the management has not been giving very high or high attention to communicate clearly to the employees the strategic direction of the college to their employees, involve the employees in discussing the strategic direction of the college, coordinate different work to accomplish the vision and mission, explain the decisions to the employees and clarify policy guidelines. Pijnacker (2019) found in her study that employees who experience clarity are more efficient and effective compared to those who have no clarity with their responsibilities.

Table 2: Organizational Climate Along with Standards

Statements	Mean	Descriptive Interpretation
1. Employees are given challenging and achievable objectives to accomplish	3.41	SWA/Moderate
2. Employees are involved in determining and monitoring the objectives	3.32	SWA/Moderate
3. The objectives to be achieved are measurable	3.36	SWA/Moderate
4. Effective work behaviors to achieve the objectives are defined	3.31	SWA/Moderate
5. There are prescribed procedures to be followed by employees in carrying out their jobs	3.38	SWA/Moderate
6. Quality standards are clearly defined and understood by employees	3.38	SWA/Moderate
Composite Mean	3.36	SWA/Moderate

Source: Hey Group (2003)

It is the same case with the standards dimension. As reflected on the table, the data reveals that as a whole, the organizational climate of Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos region along *standard dimension* gains a composite mean of 3.36 which is interpreted as “somewhat agree” or “Moderate extent”. This composite mean manifests that the organizational climate of Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos region along a standard dimension is not very high or high and it is not also very low or low but at a moderate level. Even if the items are taken separately, they all show the same level of assessment which fall within the same interpretation as "somewhat agree or moderate" such as: "employees are given challenging and achievable objectives to accomplish (3.41), involved in determining and monitoring the objectives (3.32), the objectives to be achieved are measurable (3.36), effective work behaviors to achieve the objectives are defined (3.31), there are prescribed procedures to be followed by employees in carrying out their jobs (3.38), and quality standards are clearly defined and understood by employees (3.38).

The evaluation reflects a situation in which the management or the administrators have not been exerting very high or high effort to assign challenging objectives to be accomplished by employees, involve the employees in determining and monitoring the accomplishment of the objectives, assign measurable objectives, define behaviors required to achieve the objectives, establish clear procedures to be followed to achieve the objectives and define the quality standards. As a result of such a situation, the employees have no clear idea of what to achieve and how to achieve them. Ashraf, et.al. (2017) confirmed that there is a positive correlation between performance standards and job performance.

Table 3: Organizational Climate Along with Responsibility

Statements	Mean	Descriptive Interpretation
1. There is a delegation of authority down to the lower level 1 2 3 4 5	3.36	SWA/Moderate
2. Minimum number of interference to ensure autonomy 1 2 3 4 5	3.34	SWA/Moderate
3. Employees are encouraged to cooperate, communicate and practice teamwork on their own 1 2 3 4 5	3.43	SWA/Moderate
4. Provide sufficient room for employees to take initiative and calculated risks 1 2 3 4 5	3.40	SWA/Moderate
5. Holds employees accountable for their performance 1 2 3 4 5	3.40	SWA/Moderate
6. Coaches and counsels employees to manage their problems – solving efforts 1 2 3 4 5	3.35	SWA/Moderate
Composite Mean	3.38	SWA/Moderate

Source: Hey Group(2003)

As it is gleaned from the data, it appears that as a whole, the organizational climate of Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos region in terms of responsibility receives a composite mean of 3.38 which can be interpreted as “somewhat agree or moderate level”. This composite mean concludes that the organizational climate of the Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos region in terms of responsibility is not very high or high and it is also not very low or low but to a moderate extent. Even when the items are taken singly, they all reveal the same level of assessment which is "somewhat agree or moderate extent" such as “ delegation of authority (3.36), a minimum number of interference to ensure autonomy (3.34), cooperation, communication and teamwork (3.43), providing sufficient room for employees to take initiative and calculated risks (3.40), holding employees accountable for their performance (3.40), and coaching and counseling employees to manage their problems – solving efforts (3.40).

The evaluation reveals that the management has not been very highly or highly delegating their authority to employees, minimizing interference to the work of employees, encouraging cooperation, open communication, and teamwork, allowing employees to initiate activities and take the risk, reminding the employees to be accountable to their work output and helping employees how to solve their problems. Such evaluation indicates that management is not yet ready to allow the employees to take control and responsibility for their work. Pelit, et.al. (2011) revealed that employees are satisfied when they are given responsibilities or when they are empowered to do their work on their own.

Table 4: Organizational Climate Along with Flexibility

Statements	Mean	Descriptive Interpretation
1. Encourages creativity, experimentation, and independent thinking 1 2 3 4 5	3.38	SWA/Moderate
2. People are not afraid of challenging the norms 1 2 3 4 5	3.34	SWA/Moderate
3. Less bureaucratic steps in the work process 1 2 3 4 5	3.38	SWA/Moderate
4. Be willing to accept other viewpoints that are useful 1 2 3 4 5	3.37	SWA/Moderate
5. Encourages new ideas into practice 1 2 3 4 5	3.38	SWA/Moderate
6. Works for “win-win” rather than “win-lose” solutions 1 2 3 4 5	3.31	SWA/Moderate
Composite Mean	3.36	SWA/Moderate

Source: Hey Group (2003)

As shown on the table, the data reveals that as a whole, the organizational climate of Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos region along flexibility obtains a composite mean of 3.36 which is described as “somewhat agree or moderate extent”. This composite mean demonstrates that the organizational climate of the Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos region is not very high or high and it is not also very low or very low but to a moderate extent. Even if they are taken separately, all items manifest the same level of descriptive interpretation which is “somewhat agree or moderate extent” such as “encouraging creativity, experimentation, and independent thinking (3.38), allowing employees to challenge the norms (3.34), lessening the bureaucratic steps in the work process (3.38), willingness to accept other viewpoints that are useful (3.37), encouraging new ideas into practice (3.38) and working for a win-win solution rather than a win-lose solution (3.31).

This evaluation manifests the fact that management has not been very highly or highly flexible when it comes to encouraging independent thinking and creativity, allowing employees to challenge the established norms, minimizing bureaucracy to make things fast, encouraging employees to come up with new ideas and practice it, and working on a compromised deal to problems. There is a lack of flexibility from the management side. Davidescu, et.al. (2020) found that flexibility affects the job satisfaction of employees.

Table 5: Organizational Climate Along with Rewards & Recognition

Statements	Mean	Descriptive Interpretation
1. Provides detailed performance standards to both individual employees and teams/departments	3.29	SWA?Mode rate
2. Employees are rewarded in time and performance-based	3.08	SWA/Mode rate
3. Advancement opportunities are provided for talented employees	3.18	SWA/Mode rate
4. There are non-monetary ways of rewarding individual and group performance	3.29	SWA/Mode rate
5. There are opportunities for promotion for those who perform	3.26	SWA/Mode rate
6. Management is humble enough to express expressing their positive feedbacks to employees who accomplish their job well	3.23	SWA/Mode rate
Composite Mean	3.22	SWA/Mode rate

Source: Hey Group (2003)

As indicated in the table of data, it shows that as a whole, the organizational climate of the Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos region in terms of reward and recognition receives a composite mean of 3.22 which can be interpreted as “somewhat agree or moderate extent”. It means that the organizational climate of the Divine Word Colleges along rewards and recognition is not very high or high and it is not also very low or low but to a moderate extent. Even if the questions are taken separately, they all indicate the same level of assessment which falls within the same descriptive interpretation of “somewhat agree or moderate extent” such as “providing performance standards (3.28) and rewarding employees based on performance (3.08), advancement opportunity for talented employees (3.18), providing non-monetary ways of rewarding individual and group performance (3.29), promoting those who perform (3.26), and providing positive feedback for employees who accomplished their task (3.23).

Such evaluation points out that management has not been very highly or highly providing performance standards and performance rewards, promoting talented employees, providing non-monetary ways to individual and group performance, and motivating

employees through giving positive feedback to employees who perform. Baskar (2013) had studied the impact of rewards and recognition on employee motivation and he found that rewards and recognition affect motivation and job satisfaction.

Table 6: Organizational Climate Along with Team Commitment

Statements	Mean	Descriptive Interpretation
1. There is cooperation among employees to accomplish the goals	3.37	SWA/Moderate
2. Provides ways for people to get to know each other in non-working settings	3.30	SWA/Moderate
3. Identifies team symbols that create a common identity	3.46	SWA/Moderate
4. Sets up systems for cooperation, rather than competition	3.46	SWA/Moderate
5. Ensures that diversity is valued	3.38	SWA/Moderate
6. Structures decision-making to include team input	3.40	SWA/Moderate
Composite Mean	3.40	SWA/Moderate

Source: Hey Group (2003)

As presented on the table, the data displays that as a whole, the organizational climate of the Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos region in terms of team commitment obtains a composite mean of 3.40 which is described as "somewhat agree or moderate extent". Such description points toward a fact that the organizational climate of the Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos region is not very high or high and it is also not very low or low but to a moderate extent. Even if the items are taken separately, they all reveal the same descriptive interpretation of "somewhat agree or moderate extent" such as, "cooperation among employees to accomplish the goals (3.37), providing ways for people to get to know each other in non-working settings (3.30), identifying team symbols that create a common identity (3.46), setting up systems for cooperation, rather than competition (3.46), ensuring diversity is valued (3.38) and structuring decision making to include team inputs (3.40).

The composite mean manifests that the management has not been very highly or highly ensuring cooperation among employees to accomplish the goals, initiating activities for the employees to get to know each other, identifying symbols that create a common identity, making a system to promote cooperation and not a competition, creating a workplace environment where diversity is valued and recognized and providing an environment in which all inputs are recognized and respected. Neiningger, et.al. (2010) had studied the effect of team and organizational commitment and they found that team commitment affects team performance and altruistic behavior.

Table 7: Organizational Climate Summary Table

Statements	Composite Mean	Descriptive Interpretation
Clarity	3.27	SWA/Moderate
Standards	3.36	SWA/Moderate
Responsibility	3.38	SWA/Moderate
Flexibility	3.36	SWA/Moderate
Rewards & Recognition	3.22	SWA/Moderate
Team Commitment	3.40	SWA/Moderate
Overall Mean	3.33	SWA/Moderate

Source: Hey Group (2003) and Drigo Consulting Group (2003).

The summary table reflects it all. As it is indicated in the table, the data shows that the overall mean for the organizational climate is 3.33 which is described as somewhat agree or moderate extent. Such an overall mean rating concludes that the organizational climate of the Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos region is not very high or high and it is not also very low or low. Even after looking into the dimensions of organizational climate, all dimensions of organizational climate are perceived to be moderate such as clarity (3.27), standards (3.36), responsibility (3.38), Flexibility (3.36), rewards and recognition (3.22), and team commitment (3.40). The evaluation indicates that the management needs to improve the organizational climate along the identified dimensions. Berberoglu (2018) had conducted a study on the effect of good organizational climate on organizational commitment, and performance and the study found that organizational climate affects organizational commitment and organizational performance.

Problem 2: What is the work engagement of employees of Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos Region in terms of

- 2.1. Cognitive engagement
- 2.2. Affective engagement
- 2.3. Conative engagement?

Table 8: Cognitive Work Engagement

Statements	Mean	Descriptive Interpretation
1. My mind is often full of ideas about my work	3.63	A/High
2. My mind is fully engaged with my work	3.65	A/High
3. I have an idea about how to perform my work better	3.69	A/High
4. I search for new ways to improve my knowledge related to my work	3.70	A/High
5. My thoughts are fully focused when thinking about my work	3.66	A/High
Composite Mean	3.67	Agree/High

Source: Kuok and Taormina (2017)

As gleaned from the data, it appears that as a whole, work engagement of employees of the Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos region in terms of cognitive engagement obtains a composite mean of 3.67 which is described as “agree or high”. Such composite mean indicates that work engagement of employees is high but not very high and it is also not moderate, low, or very low. Even if the items are taken separately, all items are falling within the same range of interpretation which is “agree or high”, such as “their mind is full of ideas about the work (3.63), their mind is fully engaged with their work (3.65), they have the idea about how to perform their work better (3.69), they search for new ways to improve their knowledge related to their work (3.70), and their thoughts are fully focused when they are thinking about their work (3.66).

This rating points out that the employees of the Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos region are highly engaged in their work. They have the knowledge about their work and their mind are fully engaged in their work, have the idea on how to carry out their work, keep on improving their work by getting more new knowledge about their work, and are fully focused on their work.

Table 9: Emotional Work Engagement

Statements	Mean	Descriptive Interpretation
1. I feel very delighted about what I am doing whenever I am working	3.69	A/High
2. I am excited to do my work	3.70	A/High
3. I feel good about the work that I do	3.66	A/High
4. I am always very enthusiastic to perform my work.	3.74	A/High
5. I feel very happy when I carry out my responsibilities at work.	3.74	A/High
Composite Mean	3.71	Agree/High

Source: Kuok and Taormina (2017)

As presented in the table, the data reveals that as a whole, the work engagement of the employees of the Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos region along emotional dimension gains a composite mean of 3.71 which is described as "agree or high". This means that the work engagement of employees is high but not very high and it is not also moderate, low, or very low. Even when the items are taken singly, they all are rated within the same level of description which is "agree or high" such as feeling delighted about what they are doing (3.69), feeling excited to do their work (3.70), feeling good with the work they do (3.66), feeling enthusiastic to perform their work (3.74) and feeling happy when they are carrying out their duties and responsibilities at work (3.74).

The composite mean suggests that the emotional work engagement of employees of the Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos region is high but not very high. In short in general, employees agree that they are happy with their work.

Table 10: Physical Work Engagement

Statements	Mean	Descriptive Interpretation
1. No matter how much I work, I still have a high level of energy	3.61	A/high
2. I have a great deal of stamina for my work	3.64	A/High
3. I have a lot of energy for my work	3.64	A/high
4. I am frequently energized by my work	3.68	A/High
5. Though my work is physically challenging, I am still excited to do it	3.69	A/High
Composite Mean	3.65	Agree/High

Source: Kuok and Taormina (2017)

As reflected on the table, the data shows that as a whole, the work engagement of employees of the Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos region in terms of physical engagement garnered a composite mean of 3.63 which is interpreted as "agree or high". This rating points out that the physical work engagement of employees is high but not very high, and it is not also moderate, low, or very low. Even when the items are taken separately, they are all evaluated with the same level of interpretation which is "agree or high" such as "having a high level of energy (3.61), having a great deal of stamina in their work (3.64), having a lot of energy for their work

(3.64), feeling energized by their work 93.68), and feeling excited to do their work even though the work is physically challenging (3.69).

The evaluation reveals that the physical work engagement of employees is considered high in terms of their level of energy and stamina invested in their work, and feeling excited still to perform their work even though the work is challenging.

Table 11: Work Engagement Summary Table

Components	Mean	Descriptive Interpretation
Cognitive engagement	3.67	A/High
Emotional engagement	3.71	A/High
Physical engagement	3.65	A/High
Overall Mean	3.68	Agree/High

Source: Kuok and Taormina (2017).

The summary table reveals that overall, the work engagement of employees of the Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos region is considered high as indicated by its overall mean rating of 3.68. It just means that the work engagement of employees is high but not very high and it is also not moderate, low, or very low. Even when the components are evaluated separately, they all are evaluated within the same range of interpretation which is "agree or high" such as cognitive engagement 93.67), emotional engagement (3.71), and physical engagement (3.65).

The overall mean rating concludes that the work engagement of employees of the Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos region is considered high but not very high. Though it is high, however, there is a need for improvement.

Problem 3: Is there a relationship between organizational climate and work engagement of employees?

Table 12: Coefficients of correlation on the relationship between the organizational climate and work engagement of employees

Organizational commitment		Work engagement			
		Cognitive Engagement	Work Engagement	Emotional Engagement	Physical Work Engagement
Clarity	Pearson Correlation	.567**		.620**	.601**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000
Standards	Pearson Correlation	.663**		.712**	.692**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000
Responsibility	Pearson Correlation	.590**		.634**	.627**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000
Flexibility	Pearson Correlation	.565**		.635**	.619**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000
Rewards and Recognition	Pearson Correlation	.454**		.467**	.433**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000
Team Commitment	Pearson Correlation	.595**		.639**	.602**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000

**Correlation is significant at .01 level

Pearson r correlation table indicates that there is a very significant correlation between organizational climate and work engagement at a .01 level of significance. Even when the dimensions of organizational climate are taken separately, it shows that all the dimensions of organizational climate such as clarity, standards, responsibility, flexibility, rewards, and recognition, and team commitment are significantly correlated to different dimensions of work engagement such as cognitive work engagement, emotional work engagement, and physical work engagement.

The findings indicate that the higher or the better the organizational climate is, the better the work engagement of employees becomes. In other words, solving the problem of work engagement is necessary to improve the independent variables or organizational climate.

Result and Discussion

The main purpose of the study is to determine the correlation between organizational climate and work engagement of employees. And the result indicates that both variables are correlated. Such a result suggests that managers need to improve the organizational climate of the organization to improve the work engagement of individual employees and even group engagement (Bakis, 2015).

Failing to improve the organizational climate such as clarity, standards, responsibility, flexibility, rewards and recognition and team commitment can diminish the work engagement of employees. Diminishing work engagement can mean many things such as low productivity, quality of product, profit, and failing to achieve the organizational goals and consequently weakens its competitive advantage (Bakker, Schaufeli, Leiter, & Taris, 2008). It has been pointed out by different studies that low-level work engagement is one of the main causes of the economic problem around the world (Motyka, 2018). In the school context, diminishing work engagement or diminishing teaching engagement of teachers can affect the students' academic engagement (Cardwel, 2011, Ortiz, 1997) and the school performance (Ozgenel & Mert, 2019).

The result of the study helps the management to look into the factors that affect the organizational climate and find ways to improve the climate. The quality of education can never be separated from quality teachers and employees who are engaging in their work (Bonney, et.al., 2015). School performance, whatever it means is always correlated with the performance of teachers (Lamas, 2015). Salamat, et.al. (2013) contended that students' performance is the result of teacher's performance and teacher's performance is correlated with the organizational climate. Further, they recommended to the Principals to determine factors that would promote a better environment for teachers to teach well in the classroom. A similar finding was also presented by Khan (2019) on the effect of organizational climate on teachers' commitment. The study support finding of Salamat (2013) that organizational climate enhances teachers' commitment.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study as reflected in the data, the study concludes that the organizational climate of the Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos region is considered moderate and the work engagement of employees is considered high. The Pearson r correlation indicated that there is a correlation between organizational climate and work engagement of employees of the Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos region. Therefore the hypothesis of the study is accepted.

The finding of the study contributes important discussion to school administrators on how to manage better school management. It provides important insights into the role of organizational climate to enhance quality education. However, the study also recognizes its limitation. The study limits its investigation to only six dimensions of organizational climate such as clarity, standards, responsibility, flexibility, rewards and recognition, and team commitment, and the population of the study limits to only colleges in the Ilocos region. It needs to broaden its investigation to include many dimensions of organizational climate and to include a wider population which may include all the Divine Word Colleges in Region One, Philippines.

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